

Security Assessment of Authentication Protocols in Mobile Adhoc Networks

Megha Soni
Assistance Professor
SVCE, Indore India
meghasoni@svceindore.ac.in

Brijendra Kumar Joshi
Professor MCTE,
MCTE, Mhow India
brijendrajoshi@yahoo.com

Abstract—Mobile Ad-hoc Networks can be easily targeted by different attacks such as Denial of Service, Wormhole and Man-in-the-Middle. A packet authentication is required in wireless communication to combat such attacks from outsider nodes. We have found out the parameters by which security of different protocols like HEAP, LHAP, TESLA, and Lu and Pooch's can be assessed. Also vulnerabilities of these protocols for different attacks have been discussed. To grade the performance of these authentication protocols, different parameters such as throughput, latency and packet delivery ratio have been used.

Index Terms—HEAP, Authentication, Security, MANETs

I. INTRODUCTION

Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs) are getting noteworthy attention from industry and research area due to its versatile applications and security challenges. For example, in military applications, for infrastructure-less networks, MANETs are able to exchange strategic information and perform with high mobility. MANETs are also suitable for mobile conferencing in a big group of people. It can be quickly installed in emergencies like disaster management situations [1].

MANETs have to offer different levels of security in various applications for their successful utilization. However, due to absence of central authority and wireless links among nodes, they have much greater security issues than wired networks. An attacker can easily join or leave and snoop a network, as physical link is not required. Their aim is to disrupt the network, drop packets or inject fake packets. As a result, it is easy to launch Denial of Service (DoS) attack, Man-in-the-Middle attack and Wormhole attacks or imitate another node.

To improve MANET's security, different schemes such as secure routing using symmetric and asymmetric cryptography for key establishment and distribution have been proposed [2]. But, all these protocols are able to authenticate only control packets. If these are used for authentication of data packets, network overhead would increase. On the other hand,

unauthenticated data packets make protocols vulnerable for different routing attacks, as it is essential to authenticate control and data packets both to provide guard against different attacks. Many authentication protocol like Hop-by-Hop Efficient Authentication Protocol (HEAP), Lightweight Hop-by-Hop Authentication Protocol (LHAP), Timed Efficient Stream Loss-tolerant Authentication (TESLA) and Lu and Pooch's algorithm have been designed to authenticate both types of packets.

II. AUTHENTICATION IN MANETS

In this process, an authentication protocol is used by authenticator to verify credentials presented by a supplicant. In this way supplicant's access privileges are established by the authenticator. Such an authentication protocol may also use a Trusted Third Party (TTP) during such a process. Here an supplicant is defined as an entity seeking access of protected resources through an authenticator, which is an entity that controls access to some resources. Further, it makes authentication decisions during the authentication process. A sequence of messages are exchanged between entities to identify each other. Here either supplicant or authenticator distribute secrets or allow secrets to be recognized. Further, an identifier that is used to authenticate a supplicant with high confidence is called a credential. Also, an entity trusted by both, supplicant and authenticator, is called TTP.

III. NEED OF AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOLS

Communication links in MANETs, in contrast to fixed networks, are open shared medium. As a result, communication between neighboring nodes is more vulnerable to attacks. In MANETs, due to constrained resources; limited battery power, small computational capacity and rapid changes in topography; both data packet delivery and authentication protocol used for routing need to be scalable and light weight. In MANETs, techniques such as asymmetric cryptography, being very intensive, are prohibitively insufficient due to associated computational complexity and message overhead. Contrastingly, symmetric cryptographic algorithms are fast; yet

complex in key maintenance, thus it creates difficulty in authentication of multicast and broadcast communication.

Need for efficient and large-scale data dissemination is driving popularity of broadcast communication. Ability of broadcast networks to distribute packets to multitude of receivers also frequently facilitates malicious users to impersonate as a sender and inject packets in a broadcast network. This gives rise to need for authentication protocol which will enable receivers to verify that a given received packet was indeed sent by the claimed sender.

Appending a Message Authentication Code (MAC); generated by use of a shared secret key; as usually deployed in point-to-point authentication mechanism; is actually insufficient to provide secure broadcast authentication. This is because any receiver with a secret key can forge data and function as a sender. To prevent such attacks, asymmetric cryptographic protocol becomes a natural choice. While its action of signing each data packet indeed provides secured broadcast authentication, it is associated with high overhead, time required to sign and verify as well as the consequent use of bandwidth.

There are many techniques which gradually reduce this overhead by using single signature over several packets; yet none of those offer complete satisfaction about their bandwidth deployed, scalability and processing time in network. And as against this, serious vulnerabilities against attacks; like DoS, replay attack, Man-in-the-Middle attack and Wormhole attack are possible. If data packets are unauthenticated, loss of robustness to packets loss are observed. Serious attacks like DoS are possible. If an attacker floods the receiver with bogus packets supposedly containing a signature while authentication deploying schemes amortize a digital signature over multiple data packets. The receiver gets overwhelmed while verifying bogus signatures as the signature verification being computationally costly.

Researchers have recognized that to protect against such attacks, it is important to authenticate both data as well as control packets; and have accordingly designed requisite authentication protocols.

IV. AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOLS

In TESLA [3], packets are not authenticated at every Hop; instead it uses end-to-end authentication in which packets are authenticated by final receiver, that too after a delay of several seconds. As a result, TESLA's throughput for mobile nodes is mediocre and suffers from long latency. Moreover, it also requires loose time synchronization between sender and receiver.

LHAP is built on principles of TESLA and it makes an attempt to overcome its drawbacks. Actually, LHAP was

designed for MANETs and makes use of Hop-by-Hop authentication [4].

It deploys twin techniques of lightweight packet authentication and lightweight trust management and is consequently more efficient compared to traditional authentication algorithms. It is characterized by reduced number of public key operations as it makes use of TESLA for trust bootstrapping and maintaining trust relationships among a set of nodes. LHAP employs one-way hash chains in packet authentication technique.

Lu and Pooch's algorithm is based on LHAP. Even this algorithm uses Hop-by-Hop authentication and is known to be efficient like LHAP[5][6]. Yet, it uses only one key at every node instead of two as used by LHAP. Lu and Pooch's algorithm makes use of 'delayed key disclosure' like TESLA; resulting in network latency.

HEAP is independent of routing protocol used. It is suited for most applications, whether unicast, multicast or broadcast. It is very efficient protocol as it uses two keys and is based on modified HMAC algorithm [7].

In HEAP; as and when due to mobility, a given node's neighborhood alters; the said node shares the *Ikey* and a new *Okey* with each new neighbor. Even TESLA, LHAP and Lu function on similar lines. These keys need to expire after a certain amount of time and new keys should be generated, e.g. after every few hours is another requirement. This is one way to guard against crypt-analysis attacks by an adversary.

V. SECURITY ATTACKS ON AUTHENTICATION PROTOCOLS

Authentication Protocols in MANETs are prone to different types of attacks on their mechanism. Such attacks are mainly divided into two groups [4]; Outsider attack and Insider attack.

A. Outsider Attacks

Outsider attacks are defined as attacks from nodes which do not hold a valid certificate. Such attacks are further classified into two types.

1) *Single Outsider Attack*: This type of attack is possible when a valid node moves out of the range of other nodes for a period of time; and this transmitting node is not aware of the absence of node. Further, transmitting node happens to have disclosed its TESLA and TRAFFIC keys for the said time period and a malicious node now obtains these keys and uses the same to pretend a node from the network.

2) *Collaborative Outsider Attack* : Wormhole attack [8] is a type of collaborative outsider attack. It is launched by multiple attackers. These attackers form a private tunnel by which they communicate directly. For example, node A wants to send packets to node E but node P1 eavesdropped key messages and traffic packets of node A and forwards to P2 via

a wormhole tunnel. Then P2 can alter and rebroadcast to node E.

B. Insider attack

These attacks are launched by one or more nodes which are compromised and hold legal certificates. Insider attacks can be classified in to two types.

1) *Single / Multiple Insider Attack* : To increase the traffic inside the networks a compromised node may try to flood many traffic packets into the network. These attacks can be initiated by many compromised nodes which were legitimate previously.

2) *Insider Clone Attack* : When a compromised legitimate node shares its identity or private key with an outsider attacker node and both holding the same identity. It is less likely to detect an outsider node. The cloned nodes are mostly spread in different network areas. The collaborative attack by these nodes is called clone attack.

A few important attacks that affect authentication protocols are: Man-In-The Middle attack and DoS attack. In case of Man-In-The Middle, the attacker impersonates both sender as well as the receiver with respect to each other and without their knowledge of attack. In this attack, which is also called Bucket Brigade attack, the attacker is actively eavesdropping upon the link between the verifier and the prover and thereby intercepting all authentication messages being exchanged by the sender and the receiver in the network under attack [9].

In DoS attack, an attacker causes unnecessary communication delay in data reaching its destination or network traffic is dropped altogether or even redirected to another destination.

TABLE I. ATTACKS ON PROTOCOLS

Name of Protocol	Attack		
	<i>Man in Middle</i>	<i>Wormhole</i>	<i>DoS</i>
Lu and Pooch's	No	No	Yes
TESLA	No	Yes	Yes
LHAP	Yes	Yes	Yes
HEAP	No	No	No

Source authentication schemes like TESLA having an upper bound limit on traffic rate but it can prevent some attacks on MANETs. In case of Hop-by-Hop authentication every node authenticates only neighborhood nodes in place of the sources of original traffic, compromised node is able to pretending itself as a valid forwarding node and transmits malicious traffic

inside the network. It does not offer strong source authentication,

TESLA, LHAP and Lu and Pooch's algorithm refer Table I are vulnerable to DoS attack and requires that all the nodes should be synchronized in time [7]. To prevent TESLA, LHAP and Lu algorithm from certain attacks, it is required that when a node moves from the range, one or two keys should be exchanged with all new neighbor nodes. The keys should be valid for fix time and after that it should expire and a new key should be generated for same time period.

To prevent "Man in-the-Middle" attacks from the TESLA it uses delayed key disclosure. LHAP is vulnerable to Wormhole and Man-in-the-Middle attacks refer Table I because periodic delayed key disclosure is not used in these algorithms [4].

HEAP offers some level of protection against insiders who try to forge packets and impersonate other insiders in order to incriminate them. Any packet transmitted by an outsider node should be immediately dropped by the receiving insider node at the first hop with a very high probability.

HEAP successfully guards against many outsider attacks refer Table I, such as DoS attack that attempt to flood the network, Wormhole attack, Man-in-the-Middle attack, and Flooding etc. [7].

VI. SECURITY PARAMETERS

Security of any protocol can be assessed by following parameters-

- Protocol is based on source authentication or hop by hop authentication.
- Technique used for message broadcasting, whether protocol is multicast or unicast.
- Algorithm used for trust maintenance in authentication.
- No. of Keys used in trust bootstrapping.
- Condition of trust termination between two nodes.
- Use of symmetric cryptography (Digital Signature) in trust management.
- Delayed authentication with indexing in transmission.
- Delay time of key disclosure
- Use of varied delay in key disclosure

VII. PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS

The performance metrics employed to analyze different protocols are- Authentication Latency, Throughput, and Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR).

A. Authentication Latency

The latency in a packet authentication is due to MAC verification and delay key disclosure. The latency of MAC verification is less than one millisecond and it is due to computing one hash. The latency in packet authentication is mainly due to the key disclosure delay. The value of key disclosure delay is based on current traffic pattern and it is decided by the packet sender.

B. Throughput

Mean Throughput can be defined as the ratio of the number of packets successfully received by each node and total simulation time [10].

C. PDR

PDR is measured as the ratio of number of packets successfully received by each node and total number of packets sent [10].

Authors [7] have performed the simulation on GloMoSim v2.03. Following approximate values of Mean latency variation (Table II), PDR variation (Table III) and Throughput variation (Table IV) are found by the study of simulation results graph of TESLA, LHAP, Lu Pooch's algorithm and HEAP.

Mean latency of HEAP is very low as compared to other protocols.

In case of TESLA, LHAP and HEAP, the peak value of PDR (Table III) is reached approximately 85% at packet rate 20 packets/sec. Initially PDR remains constant up to 25 pkts/sec. As can be seen, at higher packet rates, PDR quickly reduces and tapers off to around 10%, as the throughput is a function of the product of the PDR and packet rate.

The peak value of throughput (Table IV) is reached at 25 packets/sec, because throughput is proportional to product of the PDR and packet rate. For high packet rate throughput falls sharply cutting with PDR but for packet rate more than 50 packets/sec. throughput is nearly constant and effect of low PDR is offset by the high packet rate.

The performance of Lu's algorithm is significantly poorer than all other algorithms in both PDR and throughput. It is due to caches of packets at first forwarding nodes. First forwarding node cached packets until it would not receive a key update packet.

TABLE I. VARIATION OF MEAN LATENCY

S.No.	Number of Hops	Protocol			
		LHAP	HEAP	TESLA	Lu Pooch's
1	1	1000	4	20000	2000
2	2	1000	10	20000	6000
3	3	1000	12	25000	9000
4	4	1000	14	30000	10000
5	5	1000	16	35000	11000

TABLE II. PDR (%) VARIATION

S.No.	Packet Rate (Pkts / sec)	Protocol			
		LHAP	HEAP	TESLA	Lu Pooch's
1	20	85	85	85	40
2	40	36	36	36	19
3	60	21	20	20	10
4	80	16	16	15	9
5	100	15	15	13	9

TABLE III. VARIATION OF THROUGHPUT(bytes/s)

S.No.	Packet Rate (Pkts / sec)	Protocol			
		LHAP	HEAP	TESLA	Lu Pooch's
1	20	8800	8800	8800	4000
2	40	7200	7200	7200	3700
3	60	6800	6000	6800	3500
4	80	6900	6600	6500	3900
5	100	6900	6600	6300	4700

VIII. CONCLUSION

We compared the performance of HEAP, TESLA, LHAP and Lu and Pooch's algorithms and it is observed that TESLA is vulnerable to DoS attack and requires secure time synchronization of all the nodes. It introduces very large latencies of several seconds making it unsuitable for real time or QoS applications. LHAP is vulnerable to Wormhole and Man-in-the Middle attack. It also has very large memory requirements at every node. Lu's scheme has overall poor performance. In this scheme, throughput and PDR significantly degrade. It has extremely low memory requirements. HEAP is resistant to several outsider attacks such as DoS, Wormhole, Replay. HEAP is suitable for use in MANETs for unicast, multicast or broadcast applications.

IX. REFERENCES

- [1]. Perkins, C. E. "Ad hoc Networking", Pearson Publication, India, 2008,
- [2]. M. Soni, and B. K. Joshi, "Security Assessment of SAODV Protocols in Mobile Ad-hoc Networks", Proceeding of the International Symposium Data Science and Big Data Analytics (ISDB ACM-WIR 2018), Indore; 5-6 January 2018, pp. 347-355.
- [3]. A. Perrig, R. Canetti, J. D. Tygar, and D. Song; "The TESLA Broadcast Authentication Protocol", Journal of Crypto Bytes, vol. 5, no. 2, Summer / Fall, 2002, pp. 2-13.
- [4]. S. Zhu, S. Xu, S. Setia, and S. Jajodia, "LHAP: A Lightweight Hop-by-hop Authentication Protocol for Ad-Hoc Networks", Proceeding of 23rd IEEE International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems Workshops(ICDCSW03), Providence, USA, 19-22 May 2003, pp. 749.
- [5]. Lu and U. W. Pooch, "A Lightweight Authentication Protocol for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks", Proceeding of the IEEE International Conference on Information Technology (ITCC'05), Las Vegas, USA, 4-6 April 2005, pp. 546-551.
- [6]. Lu and U. W. Pooch, "A Lightweight Authentication Protocol for Mobile Ad Hoc Networks", International Journal of Information Technology, vol. 11, no. 2, 2005, pp. 119-135.
- [7]. R. Akbani, T. Korkmaz and G.V.S. Raju; "HEAP: Hop-by-hop Efficient Authentication Protocol For Mobile Ad-hoc Networks", Proceeding of the Spring Simulation Multiconference, SpringSim 2007, Norfolk, Virginia, USA, 25-29 March 2007, pp. 157-165.
- [8]. B. K. Joshi and M. Soni; "Security Assessment of AODV Protocol under Wormhole and DOS Attacks", Proceeding of the 2nd International IEEE Conference on Contemporary Computing and Informatics (IC3I2016), Noida , India, 14-17 December 2016, pp. 173-177.
- [9]. N. Pari S, "Investigation of malicious nodes by security improvisation of routing in mobile ad hoc networks", PhD Dissertation, Anna University, Chennai 2014, pp. 111-112.
- [10]. Megha Soni, and Brijendra Kumar Joshi; "Security Assessment of Routing Protocols in Mobile Ad-hoc Networks"; Proceeding of the International IEEE Conference on ICT in Business, Industry and Government (ICTIBIG2016) Indore; 18-19 November 2016, pp. 24.
- [11]. M. Soni, and B. K. Joshi, "Security Assessment of DSDV Protocol in MANET", International Journal of Advance Computational Engineering and Networking (IJACEN), vol. 5, no. 9, September 2017, pp. 107-111.

AUTHORS PROFILE

Megha Soni doing PhD research work at Electronics and Telecommunication Department of MCTE, Mhow, DAVV University Indore, India. She has obtained BE in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from Govt Engg College, Sagar; M.E in Digital Communication from Davi Ahilya University Indore. She joined as an Assistant Professor in Electronics & Communication in Dec. 2005. Her research interest is in security assessment of routing and authentication protocols of Mobile Ad Hoc Networks.

Dr Brijendra Kumar Joshi is associated with as a Professor of Electronics & Telecommunication and Computer Engineering at Military College of Telecommunication Engineering, MHOW (MP), India. He has obtained BE in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from Govt Engg College, Jabalpur; ME in Computer Science and Engineering from IISc, Bangalore, PhD in Electronics and Telecommunication Engineering from Rani Durgavati University, Jabalpur, and MTech in Digital Communication from MANIT, Bhopal. He has more than 34 years of teaching experience. His research interests are programming languages, compiler design, digital communications, mobile ad-hoc and wireless sensor networks, image processing, software engineering and formal methods. He has number of research publications to his credit. He has supervised six Ph D thesis and currently supervising nine research scholars. He has authored two books on Data Structures and Algorithms in C/C++ published by Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi.